

The Use of 1-5 *Bis*(Benzylidene) Thiocarbohydrazone as an Amperometric Reagent for Lead

S. C. SHOME, M. MAJUMDAR, A. BASU and P. C. MITRA

Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta-700 073

Manuscript received 5 May 1980, revised 5 March 1981, accepted 9 June 1981

Lead has been determined amperometrically at dropping mercury electrode using 1-5 *bis* (benzylidene) thiocarbohydrazone as complexing agent. The metal amounts varying from 0.202 mg to 5.055 mg in 0.1 to $1.62 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution can be titrated with accuracy in ammoniacal potassium cyanide medium in presence of ammonium citrate in the pH range of 10.0 to 10.5. The determination of lead has been carried out in the presence of commonly associated metal ions such as Cu^{+2} , Zn^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Fe^{+2} , As^{+3} , Sb^{+3} and Mn^{+2} . Bi^{+3} and Tl^{+3} , however, interfere. The lead content in a sample of gun-metal and that of a lead ore has been determined amperometrically using the complexing agent as titrant.

A survey of literature indicates that potassium trihydroxymethylamino-methane¹, diphenyl thiovioluric acid² or chloranilic acid³ was used as chelating agent in the amperometric titration of lead, the lowest amount of the metal that could be determined being 0.508 mg, 3.105 mg, 0.808 mg respectively. None of these reagents however was found suitable for the determination of lead in presence of foreign ions. Although lead, as low as 0.132 mg, was determined by the use of diethyldithiocarbamate⁴ as complexing agent, the method was interfered by the presence of several metal ions. Shome and coworkers⁵ carried out the amperometric determination of lead with thiosalicylamide as a sulphide precipitating agent in the presence of commonly associated metal ions but the method was not sensitive enough to determine lower than 0.94 mg of the metal.

Although thiocarbohydrazones have been used as complexing agents in the preparation of several metal complexes⁶ they have not been employed so far as reagents in inorganic analysis. In the present research 1-5 *bis* (benzylidene) thiocarbohydrazone (BBTCH).

has been used as a selective and sensitive reagent in the amperometric determination of lead. The instantaneous and quantitative precipitation of lead with BBTCH in the form of a yellow granular 1 : 2 complex at room temperature from an ammoniacal potassium cyanide medium in presence of ammonium citrate in the pH range 10.0 to 10.5 has been made the basis for the determination of the metal amperometrically.

Experimental

Apparatus : A pen recording polarograph [Radel Kis (Hungary) type OH 101/1] and a Toshniwal

manual polarographic arrangement [Type CN 02A] along with a high sensitive galvanometer (the smallest division of the galvanometer's scale corresponds to 0.171 micro-ampere) were used for obtaining the polarograms of the metal ion, of the reagent and for titrations. A systronics pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Reagents : 1-5 *Bis*(benzylidene) thiocarbohydrazone (BBTCH) was prepared and purified as reported in the literature⁷. Standard solution of the reagent was made by dissolving a weighed quantity of the triple-recrystallized BBTCH (from acetic acid solution) in dimethylsulphoxide (distilled) and the volume was made up with rectified spirit. The reagent solution finally contained 10% DMSO. A stock solution of lead nitrate (E Merck-Germany) was prepared in double distilled water and the lead content was determined by chromate method. All other chemicals used in the experiments were of A. R. or G. R. grade.

Composition of the complex : Lead was precipitated from an ammoniacal potassium cyanide medium in presence of ammonium citrate containing 10% alcohol in the pH range 10.0-10.5 with the reagent (avoiding excess) in hot condition. The precipitate was digested on a boiling water-bath for about 30 minutes, filtered, washed with 10% alcohol and dried at 110°. The complex was then decomposed with conc. $HNO_3-H_2SO_4$ mixture and the amount of lead was determined by the chromate method. Sulphur content of the complex was estimated by the sulphate method.

	Pb (%)	S (%)
Experimental results	26.70	8.51
Theoretical values for 1 : 2 lead complex	26.93	8.32

It can be seen from above that lead forms a 1 : 2 complex with the reagent in ammoniacal potassium cyanide medium in presence of ammonium citrate.

Amperometric procedure : Lead produces a well defined cathodic wave in ammoniacal potassium cyanide medium at a dropping mercury electrode. The reagent solution did not show any reduction wave upto -1.60 volt. When the solution of lead was titrated with standard BBTCH solution at an applied voltage -0.9 volt (vs S. C. E.), an L-shaped titration curve was obtained. The titrations were carried out in a simple cylindrical glass cell connected to an external saturated calomel electrode with an agar-potassium nitrate salt bridge with an average drop-time of 3.6 sec. at a height of 42 cms of the dropping mercury electrode. Different aliquots of lead solution were taken into the cell to which 3 ml of 0.1M ammonium citrate, 2 ml of 5% KCN and 2 ml of 1.0M KNO_3 (supporting electrolyte) solutions were added in each case. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 10.0-10.5 with dilute ammonia solution. The volume was made upto 10-15 ml. The titration medium was made 15% alcoholic in order to overcome the insolubility of the reagent. The solution was deaerated by passing pure nitrogen and titrated at -0.9 volt (vs S. C. E.) with BBTCH solution (1.25×10^{-2} - 1.22×10^{-3} M). Successive readings were taken after addition of small amounts of reagents and bubbling nitrogen for a short while. The end-point was obtained graphically from the L-shaped titration curve (Fig. 1) making allowances for volume change during titrations.

Fig. 1

For interference studies, known amounts of foreign ions were added and a similar procedure was followed for titration of lead.

Results and Discussion

By the present method 0.202 mg to 5.055 mg of lead present in 0.1 to 1.62×10^{-3} M solution can be determined accurately within a short time. The results are recorded in Table 1. As lead was precipitated from ammoniacal KCN medium, almost all the commonly associated metal ions did not

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF LEAD WITH BBTCH

Sl. No.	Pb taken (mg)	Pb found (mg)	error (mg)
1.	5.055	5.076	+0.021
2.	3.088	3.053	+0.02
3.	2.022	2.040	+0.018
4.	1.011	1.012	+0.001
5.	0.798	0.798	0.00
6.	0.592	0.528	-0.004
7.	0.803	0.305	+0.002
8.	0.202	0.203	+0.001

interfere. Tartrate was added in the interference study of As^{+3} , Sb^{+3} , Fe^{+3} . Although Ag^{+1} , Fe^{+3} did not interfere when present in small concentrations, they could not be tolerated in higher amounts owing to their strong polarographic waves. Determination in the presence of Sn^{+2} was possible after its prior separation as meta-stannic acid. Bi^{+3} and Tl^{+1} which reacted with the reagent under the same experimental conditions interfered. EDTA also interfered in the amperometric determination of lead. The results of the determination of lead in the presence of foreign ions are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF LEAD WITH BBTCH IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS
Lead taken - 1.011 mg

Sl. No.	Foreign ion added (mg)	Pb found (mg)	error (mg)
1.	Cu^{+2} (100)	1.017	+0.006
2.	Zn^{+2} (50)	1.011	0.00
3.	Ni^{+2} (25)	1.011	0.00
4.	Cd^{+2} (25)	0.999	-0.012
5.	Co^{+2} (10)	0.99	-0.021
6.	Mn^{+2} (10)	0.99	-0.021
7.	Pd^{+2} (10)	1.001	0.00
8.	As^{+3} (6)	1.00	-0.011
9.	Sb^{+3} (3)	1.011	0.00
10.	Ag^{+1} (1)	1.011	0.00
11.	Fe^{+3} (2)	1.00	-0.011
12.	Sn^{+2} (10)	1.021	+0.010
13.	tartrate(120)	1.00	-0.011

BBTCH is a pure and stable compound and its DMSO-ethanolic solution is quite stable when stored in a refrigerator. Lead can be determined amperometrically in the presence of almost all commonly associated metal ions. Further, as low as 0.202 mg of lead can be accurately determined by this method. Sensitivity and selectivity are, therefore, the two distinct advantages of BBTCH as an amperometric reagent for lead over the other reagents already referred.

Accuracy and Precision : The relative mean error and the coefficient of variation were calculated from a set of five experiments under identical conditions using 1.011 mg lead per 10.0 ml and found to be 0.29% and 0.86% respectively.

Technical Material Analyses : The lead contents of a sample of lead-ore and also that of gun-metal where lead is a minor constituent can be accurately determined by the amperometric method.

(i) *Lead-ore (Cerussite)* : Finely powdered cerussite (1.00 gm) was treated with 10 ml of water and 15 ml of conc. HNO_3 in a beaker, evaporated on a water bath to a volume of 5-10 ml, diluted, filtered to separate the insoluble matter and the residue washed with dilute HNO_3 . The combined filtrate and washings were made up to 250 ml with water (solution A), 10 ml of solution A was diluted to 50 ml (solution B). An aliquot (3 ml) of solution B was titrated as per procedure described earlier. The lead solution was standardised by precipitating as PbSO_4 , dissolved in ammonium acetate and estimated as PbCrO_4 . Pb found 44.17% (as determined by BBTCH method) ; Pb present 44.22% (as determined by chromate method).

(ii) *Gun-metal* : 1.00 gm of gun-metal (analysed sample supplied by Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., U. K.) was treated with 10 ml of water and 15 ml of conc. HNO_3 in a beaker and evaporated on a water-bath to a volume of 5 ml. Tin was separated as meta-stannic acid, diluted, filtered and washed with dilute HNO_3 . The filtrate and washings were evaporated, diluted to a volume of 50 ml. An aliquot (3 ml) of this solution was taken in a titration cell, 50 mg of tartrate added, followed by

3 ml of 0.1M ammonium citrate and 5 ml of 10% KCN solutions. The titration was performed according to the recommended procedure. Results : Lead found 1.14% (as determined by BBTCH method) ; Lead present 1.13%.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P. C. M.) is grateful to the University Grants Commission for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. G. S. DESHMUKH, H. CHAUDHURI and H. S. MAHANTI, *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan*, 1975, **48**, 1089.
2. N. R. BANERJEE and R. P. SINGH, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 175.
3. V. A. CORTINEZ and C. B. MARONE, *Anal. Abs.*, 1976, **31**, 58110.
4. WALTER STRICKS and S. K. CHAKRABORTY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 508.
5. S. C. SHOME, M. MAJUMDAR and A. BASU, *J. Indian Chem., Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1140.
6. RAJESHWAR SINGH and J. P. SHRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 805.
7. P. C. GUHA and SATIS CHANDRA DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 225.